

<https://www.abrj.org/>

Impact Factor 2.30

Exploring an African Political Thought: An Exposition of Nnamdi Azikiwe's "Zikism" and its Relevance in Present-day Africa.

Author Details: AYAKA Simon Silas

Department of Social Sciences-Phoenix University Agwada

Email: ayaka.silas@phoenixuniversity.edu.ng

Phone No: 08065839056

Abstract

African social and political philosophy is deeply interlaced with the daily life of Africans. Therefore, the paper explores one of the developments of this African philosophy, Zikism, which is a political philosophy or ideology propounded by Nnamdi Azikiwe, which is principally aimed at the decolonization of the minds of young Africans, in preparation for a battle against colonial Africans, brainwashed by their colonial masters. Bearing in mind that the era of colonization has come and gone, the paper x-rayed the relevance of such theory in ensuring that total emancipation from Political, social and economic neo-colonialism is achieved in Africa. It adopted the qualitative expository method to explain what the theory is, and what it stands for while outlining its relevance in present-day Africa.

Keywords: Zikism, African thought, exposition, Relevance, Nnamdi Azikiwe

INTRODUCTION

African political philosophy is a less explored field of study in comparison to research areas such as metaphysics, anthropology, theology, sociology and economics (Kanu,2007; Umezurike, 2018). Many people confine this discipline to theories of one or another African leader such as Nnamdi Azikiwe (1904-1996) Nkrumah (1909-1972), Senghor (1906-2001) and Nyerere (1922-1999). Others reduce this philosophy to both the vicissitudes and hazards of African politics in considering it as a chronicle of the ups and downs of African nations. These two approaches deform the nature of this philosophy and they skip over the effort of African people to frame rationally their social and political organization. As a reflection on the polis, African political philosophy is concerned with people's everyday life, everyday experiences of alliances and collective actions (Umezurike, 2018). This reality constitutes its roots and nourishing sap. It is advisable speaking of the "common world", to make use of Arendt's expression (makumba,2007 in Umezurike). This idea defines the political sphere as a space where people reveal themselves to each other as equal, and where they manifest their desire to build together a humanizing community. This anchoring of political philosophy in the common world is unavoidable and necessary at a time because it is how this philosophy specifies its object and forges its identity. Three classical concerns of political philosophy can be considered essential to African political philosophy viz: the well-being of African citizens, the power, and the suited paradigm for social and political organization (Makumba). The issue of the well-being of citizens is a permanent topic of political philosophy. From Socrates till to today, nobody omits this topic even if each philosopher assigns to it a particular content and sketches differently the modalities of its achievement. In this regard, African political philosophers have to deal with multiple challenges, especially; African emancipation, poverty, human rights, gender, and democracy, to mention a few. African political philosophy also addresses the issue concerning the nature and justification of power. The following questions are often asked; who governs the polis? By which principles does he/she achieve such a duty? According to what modalities and in response

to what purpose does he/she rule? The search for a suited pattern or paradigm of social and political organization has been reduced to the choice between capitalism and socialism, in Africa. For many leaders, socialism was the best option because it was thought to comply with African culture. Senghor, Nkrumah, Nyerere, Sekou Touré, and Mboya have made this option their priority (Ikenna, 1978). Many other leaders remained loyal to capitalism. This was the case for people such as Mobutu (Congo/Zaire), Ahidjo (Cameroun), Eyadema (Togo), and Bongo (Gabon) (Ikenna). Beyond this ideological option, they all remained submitted to foreign (Western) interests and policy as well as developed a philosophy of power, based on a single-party rule principle. This paper therefore seeks to examine this political ideology not just to celebrate the intellectual prowess of the late Dr. Nnamdi Azikiwe but as a possible tool for the liberation of the minds of the African youths towards ensuring that they rise to ensure good governance in all spheres of the African Continent.

Formation of Azikiwe' Political Ideas

What informed the formulation of Azikiwe's political ideas was the prevailing and pervasive contradictions of the colonial state in Africa, characterized by servitude, economic dependency, political domination and colonial exploitation, mass illiteracy, mass poverty, ignorance, fear and superstition, culminating in inferiority complex, which characterized Africans of his early experience (Umezurike, 2018). However, this condition has resurfaced in different forms thereby causing any well-meaning person to also consider formulating such political ideology like Zikism to encourage African youths to seek freedom from bad leadership, insecurity, poverty, high levels of unemployment, ethnicity and corruption which today is bedeviling our African society. To understand and link it to the present state of affairs in Africa, let us look at its tenets as it relates to the African situation

Zikism and its Tenet.

African political leadership at this period was bankrupt, ineffective, and uninspiring. The nationalist movement had been badly divided since the Ikoli- Akinsanya crisis in 1941(Nwoko,2006). The leaders, instead of uniting to challenge the colonial administration, the leaders engaged themselves with pettiness, tribalism, rancour, jealousy, and mutual antipathy. The organization which could claim a national following during this period, the National Congress of Nigerians and the Cameroons, though effective in the realm of political propaganda with its arrays of newspapers, was impotent in that of positive action. But by 1948 (National Council of Nigerian Citizens) the N.C.N.C. had ceased to be politically active. The party had been frustrated by the lack of success of the 1947 delegation it sent to Britain to protest the Richards Constitution. Eta Iyo attempted to explain the inactivity of the party by stating:

'We are not extinct, but dormant volcanoes waiting for the time when we can explode' (Ozimoro, 1978:54).

At a time when the chiefs supported British hegemony and were used to fight the liberal intelligentsia of Africa, Zik developed his philosophy as a reformist ideology. He stressed that Africa could only be emancipated by those who believed in the concept of a renascent Africa. The realization of a new Africa must not be through bloodshed or disorder. The spirit of cooperation, respect and honour for the old Africa must abound. Zikism began when Zik returned to Nigeria in the mid-30s and formed the NCNC. There was a huge mobilization of people, which created a ground for national consciousness. For this consciousness to be sustained, the development of an ideology was inevitable. This ideology took into consideration the basic views of its believers. These believers were called "agitators" by Zik. Since it was an ideology that spoke to their situation, the believers spread the ideology and organized people around it, thus transforming the ideology into a motivating instrument of action to end colonialism in Africa.

The five canons of zikism

In his political theory, Nnamdi Azikiwe enumerated five principles that are vital to the political emancipation of Africa, and they could also be referred to as the five canons of Zikism. He aimed to provide a foundational structure on which a free national political system was to be built. These canons include;

1. **Spiritual Balance:** while talking about spiritual balance, Zik called for respect for the opinions of others. This would involve allowing others the right to state their opinion without denying one's right to state his or her opinion, which can be referred to as the cultivation of the spirit of tolerant scepticism for the views of one's antagonists

2. **Social Regeneration:** Zik calls for the Jettisoning of all forms of prejudice, be they racial, national, tribal, societal, political, ethical etc. This takes us back to Francis Bacon's Idols, which are themselves prejudices. But while these prejudices in Francis Bacon impede the acquisition of knowledge, in Zikism, they impede the realization of political regeneration [5]. Nnamdi Azikiwe makes this call because an African, no matter where he or she is born, is an African. To postpone the breaking down of all forms of barriers of tribal prejudice, be they inter-tribal or intra-tribal, is to postpone the social unity of Africa

3. **Economic determinism:** Zik sees economic self-sufficiency as the ultimate means to the redemption of Africa. No matter how educated Africans may be, as long as they lack economic self-sufficiency, they will fail to realise a stable society. Education for Africans is useless unless it is adapted to the African environment. This was the idea of Zik when he called for "a state of society where the mind is brought into harmony with the matter... a psychological conception deeply rooted in a material environment" [6]; He further argues that "The usefulness of any concept, idea or theory, lies in its implications for the practical solutions to the problems of society. In this sense, pragmatism requires that man's efforts and intelligence should be geared towards the liberation of man and the satisfaction of his needs in society" (Azikiwe,1961:73); and so our education should be aimed at providing means of livelihood for Africans, to fail in this regard, Zik argues, is to dent the African social fabric (Azikiwe,1978:61)

4. **Mental Emancipation:** the slave trade and colonization of Africa created a situation of „crisis of self-confidence“ in Africa, which has opened apertures for a lasting barrier to growth and innovation. Zik argues that there is no specific proof to sustain the idea of superiority or inferiority of any race, and for the Africans to cultivate an inferiority complex is to sign the death warrant for Africa's future. He calls for emancipation from the crisis of inferiority and assures the Africans that he has a glorious past and can design a more glorious future. Zik wants the African to follow Socrates' principle: Gnothi Seauton, (Man know yourself), and like a sleeping giant wake up from his slumber and harness his power for his good and that of mankind (Azikiwe in Elias,1954:94)

5. **Political Resurgence:** If the African cultivates a spiritual balance, experiences social regeneration, cultivates and realizes economic self-sufficiency and mental emancipation, he or she certainly finds himself or herself in a state of political Risorgimento (renewal or rebirth). Zik says,

“Politics is a means to an end which is more glorious than the means through which this end must be attained. Socially, the end is the guarantee of social security, and a right to enjoy life, liberty and the pursuit of happiness, just as do other peoples. Once this is attained, a people can boast of a stable and reliable political system” (Cited in Oguejiofor,2010:58).

Zikism and African Problem

Though he wrote his treatise decades ago, his philosophy still runs deep and has astonishing relevance today in this century 21st. Since the book's publication in 1937, somehow, Africa skipped her rebirth and instead, chose the path of the still-born. And somehow, the generations between the start of the Zikist movement and the rubbles of a present-day broken continent have been sadly conspicuously silent.[10] Zik's exhortation in Renascent Africa was directed to not just the youths of Africa but also to African members of the old guard. In his time, this referred to traditional chiefs and conservative post-colonial politicians. In our time, this refers to our rulers, dictators and corrupt elites who by greed and intellectual myopia have collectively ground the continent to a halt. In Africa, he observes that numerous tribes have been united and formed a political union in the form of a federation. From this, Zik envisages a threat to national unity as is currently happening in African countries more than in any other part of the World where crises of nation-state projects have been most obvious and overwhelming. According to (Olukoshi et al, 1996), the dramatic collapse of the nation-state in Somalia, the state paralysis in Zaire, genocidal violence in Rwanda and Burundi, the organised killings carried out by government forces and Muslim fundamentalists in Algeria and Egypt, the

uneasy tension in Nigeria occasioned by Kidnappings for ransom, farmer/herder crisis all over the country, the excruciating economic hardship and the numerous low-intensity mostly ethnically-based confrontations in various parts of Africa. Also, there is an increasing salience of popular religious identities that have combined to create a sense of profound disorder on the continent. With this, Azikiwe, raises the all-important question: will the new autonomous state endure? Tribalism, he observes, is a reality, but proposes that even in tribalism, national unity can be a reality. How the reality of tribalism can be adapted to the unreality of national unity to make national unity a reality is one of the basic concerns of Zik. He enumerates the solution, which he refers to as keys:

1. To discover the circumstances which can be superimposed on the natural chains of language and culture, which have linked the human beings who inhabit Africa to enable them to develop a feeling of personal security and group preservation.
2. He proposes a federal system of government which will concede coexistence to all linguistic groups, based on equality, within a framework of political and constitutional warranties. Such a federal system of government would protect individual freedom under the rule of law and thus preserve and sustain any linguistic group. By preserving the linguistic groups of Africa and conceding to them local autonomy of some satisfactory nature, an atmosphere for respect for their culture and traditions is created.
3. If loyalty to the nation must not be replaced by loyalty to the tribe, Zik calls for a Republican Constitution: first in relation to safeguarding people's fundamental human rights; secondly, providing citizens with adequate food, comfortable shelter and a minimum level of subsistence. In this case, rulers must discover the material needs of their people. Once there is a failure of this by African rulers, Africans will harbour grievances about political, economic and social inequalities. This will increase loyalty to the tribe and disloyalty to the nation
4. An effective way to increase national unity is to concede to each region de jure equality and de facto inequality. By de jure equality, Zik speaks in the sense that every province and local authority in each region in the Federal Republic is legally equal with the federal government providing for each of them. By de facto Inequality, Zik means the acceptance of the fact that not all regions, provinces and local authorities are equal in area, population, natural resources and financial means.
5. Again, Zik argues that political parties will have to cut across the artificial barriers of tribes and regions. National loyalty must supersede regional claims.

CONCLUSION

The rise and triumph of the ethnic and regionalist tendencies in Africa has spiralled into its current headache, bred and led by her sons of Anarchy. But Zikism provides Africa with an alternative to this miasma, and on the strength of Azikiwe's renascent and humanist philosophy, this paper believes in the imperative of an African Risorgimento. It is in Africa's interest. Africa's rich human resource is its greatest strength, and might also be its major downside if improperly managed by our Leaders. The TIV themselves say, "*TYÔ hembra; kpa TYÔ ule*" A man's kinsmen are as much his strength, as they are his pains. In the Zikist context, the African problem is a class question, rather than the problem of ethnic difference. Zik taught that by harnessing the strength of Africans, everywhere in Africa, we could build great, united, and prosperous nations in Africa. Azikiwe believed in a broad-based coalition of all African ethnicities united by common economic and political interests. Africa drifts today from that vision of economic determinism, spiritual balance; social regeneration; mental emancipation; and Political resurgence. In its place has triumphed Ethnic particularism; religious fundamentalism; fascism, and dependency. The future of Africa now depends on the rise of Zikist ideas to be led by a new generation who must be taught revolutionary Zikism. Africa's problem is not the problem of "tribalism" but of elite greed, because the challenges that face the workers and peasants of North Africa are the very same that face the workers and peasants of Southern Africa. For these, the common enemy is political greed, not geographic difference. Indeed, Zik did say: "Show the light and the people will find the way."

REFERENCES

Adebayo, O Oand Liisa Laakso (1996) Challenges to the Nation-State in Africa, Motola Grafiska, Motola Press Sweden

Ayaka, S S (np), In search of African Theory of Democracy: Utilising the Tiv cultural philosophy of *ya-na-angbian*.

Kanu Ikechukwu, A.(2007) The Colonial Legacy: The Hidden History of Africa's Present Crisis, in View Point Magazine, Vol. 6, No.7, Makurdi.

Maurice Makumba, (2007) Introduction to African Philosophy. Kenya: Pauline.

Matthew Nwoko, (2006) Basic World Political Theories. In F. O. C Njoku (ed.). Enugu: Snaap Press.

Ikenna Ozimiro, (1978) Zikism and Social Thought in the Nigerian Pre-independence Period, 1944-1950 in Onigu Otite (ed). Themes in African Social and Political Thought. Malta: Fourth Dimension Publishers.

F. O. C, Njoku (2003), Empiricists and Causation in Law. Enugu: Snaap press.

Nnamdi Azikiwe (1961) Renascent Africa. New York: Negro University Press.

Nnamdi Azikiwe, (1978) From tribe to Nation, in Onigu Otite (ed.), Themes in African Social and Political Thought. Malta: Fourth Dimension Publishers.

T. O. Elias, (1954) Towards Nationhood in Nigeria. In Occasional Papers on Nigerian Affairs. London: Nigerian Society.

Umezurike G (2018) Conceptualising African Political Thoughts: An Exposition of Zikism and its Relevance in Modern Nigerian Society, In Journal of Arts and Management, International Digital Organisation for Scientific Research.www.IDOSR.org.

Oguejiofor Ezeanya, (2010) Tribe and Tongue in Nigeria. Enugu: Professor's Press.